

THE ROLE OF THE PAMPHLET GENRE IN LITERARY CRITICISM

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Abstract: Literary criticism has its own place and status in world literature and journalism. At this point, we got answers to the questions of what is criticism, what is critical thinking, and what are its features in the course of our work. Including, we thought about the role, purpose and tasks of the pamphlet genre in literary criticism. We touched on what kind of ideas the pamphlet genre actually promotes.

Key words: Publicist, literary criticism, journalism, feuilleton, pamphlet, irony, image.

The pamphlet genre, which has been forming for centuries, has gained an important importance in the history of the world press. Today's journalism, on the other hand, has become more refined as a result of such a truthful and critical approach to the life of the society, the happenings, the laws and decisions being issued.

Pamphlet is a literary genre. For this reason, it has a special place in art criticism. At this point, let's focus on literary criticism.

Literary criticism is a type of literary activity, analysis and interpretation of a work of art, as well as life events reflected in this work. Criticism is often described as a part of literary studies. But Criticism is an independent field of literary activity, unlike literary studies, it mainly observes the processes taking place in modern literary life, identifies the leading principles in this process, reacts to the literary works published in the pages of newspapers and magazines, and usually analyzes them based on the ideological and aesthetic requirements of the time. Criticism appeared almost at the same time as artistic creation.¹

¹ [https://uz.wikipedia.org/wiki/Tanqid_\(faoliyat\)](https://uz.wikipedia.org/wiki/Tanqid_(faoliyat))

Critical thinking is a complex process of combining ideas and possibilities with creativity, rethinking and reconstructing concepts and information. It is also a process that takes place simultaneously at several levels of active and interactive cognition. A critical thinker is less affected by tricks, and because of his own personal system of views, he is free from various dangers.

In critical thinking, ideas and their importance are examined from the perspective of diversity and compared to other ideas. This is the highest level of thinking, a mental activity that focuses on analyzing, comparing, interpreting, applying, arguing, innovating, solving problems, or evaluating a thought process. Critical thinking develops communication and teamwork skills.

Critical thinking is especially important in journalism. A journalist should be able to say what is right and what is wrong is wrong, and should be able to give an objective and truthful attitude to the events taking place in the life of the society. In journalism, there are critical genres with a touch of humor, in which the issue is approached with a bitter criticism. These are feleton and pamphlet genres. Although feleton and pamphlet are considered similar concepts, in fact there are certain differences between them. Both of them have a special place in literary criticism. The pamphlet genre stands out. Its uniqueness lies in the fact that the author of the pamphlet is not satisfied with empty talk, "taking away". He approaches the issue with humor and laughter. And this laugh has the power to "pierce the heart" of the hero. In this respect, pamphlets and feuilletons are part of comic journalism.

Pamphlet is one of the brightest genres of journalism. At the heart of the pamphlet, there are always signs of sarcasm, mockery, laughing at the enemy, passionate appeal to the reader. The topic of a pamphlet is usually about politics. It may contain an object of rejection, a philosophical or an aesthetic concept. The pamphlet is characterized by a sharper, negative orientation, a desire to "destroy" the enemy, and an attitude of denial. The most important features characterizing the pamphlet as a genre are the synthesis of satirical artistic and journalistic image tools; mutual political views, discussions and debates, personal critical thinking in the content of the work.

A pamphlet, like any ideological construction, always creates a new reality. His text is always a judgment based on evaluation. He relies on openness and truth in the selection of facts, images, figurative, rhetorical devices, etc. This is a topical satirical work, the meaning of which is aimed at a clear socio-political criticism aimed at completely discrediting the object of criticism. Its purpose is to arouse the reader's anger, sometimes hatred. This is especially important during times of war, including information warfare. The pamphlet genre, which goes down in history as the era of information warfare, becomes one of the most popular.

The pamphlet genre plays such an important role in literary criticism that works of each type can find their readers throughout the centuries. The person or events that become its subject are distinguished by their commitment to the fate of all mankind.

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